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Machine Learning Classifier Performance in Crop Recommendation Systems: A Systematic Review of Ensemble Versus Standalone Approaches

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ABSTRACT

Agriculture being the sector of prime importance which guarantees food security and contributes to the economy of a country, needs a robust and accurate crop growing model to achieve high yields. Advancement in the field of machine learning, has facilitated building recommendation systems that can recommend crops on various field and atmospheric attributes and contribute to real time prediction of crops. According to an analysis of research on machine learning algorithms, reported F1-scores, precision, and recall differ between ensemble and standalone classifiers. A stand-alone stochastic gradient descent classifier in one study obtained 100% F1-score, recall, and precision. Another achieved 99.2% precision, 99.4% recall, and 99.3% F1-score using an ensemble stacking technique (CaSR-Net). For standalone classifiers like random forest and severe gradient boosting, other study displayed precision values of roughly 98.5% to 99.6%; recall and F1 were not consistently reported. These results show that both standalone and ensemble methods work satisfactory when it comes to producing crop recommendations. The top-performing standalone and ensemble models displayed variations of approximately 0.5–1% across precision, recall, and F1-score when full metrics were available. In several studies, only partial metric data were reported, which limits the ability to draw broader quantitative conclusions.

Keywords:-*Ensemble, Standalone, Recommend, Classifier, Recall, Accuracy, Precision, F1-score*

INTRODUCTION

Agriculture not only ensures food security, but also forms the major contributing source to economy of many countries. It also provides employment for many people, not only farmers but also other subsidiaries and sectors, interconnected to it.

While traditional crop selection is subjective to word of mouth, or passed on knowledge from the ancestors, market opportunity etc., doesn't depend on any scientific techniques and methods of crop selection.

With the increasing use of machine learning and artificial intelligence, there can be implementation of it in the field of agriculture, horticulture, animal husbandry etc. The increased efficacy of machine learning algorithms whilst having various methods according to various parameters can leverage its super power to obtain economic and ecological yields. Not only focusing on yield, the sustainability factor of protecting the soil is also of prime importance. The soil nutrients when harnessed in right manner guarantees longevity and ensures nutritious crops.

Agricultural crop recommendation systems play important role in helping farmers to decide the crops to be grown and predict crop yields according to environmental, market and ecological factors. The recommendation systems should be capable of including soil characteristics (like nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, and pH), weather data (temperature, humidity, rainfall), and regional datasets, ML algorithms offer predictions that are at apex of that of conventional decision-making. Also integrate able with real time measures through the Internet of Things (IoT) and large datasets can further improve the prediction accuracy. Doshi, Z. et al. [1] built a machine learning approach, considering climate, season, atmospheric conditions and soil properties, which serves as the most fundamental framework for crop recommendation systems.

The variety of algorithms that can be used are Logistic regression, decision tree, k-nearest

neighbors, support vector classifier/machine, random forest, gradient boosting, bagged tree, extreme gradient boosting, AdaBoost, CatBoost, histogram-based gradient boosting, stochastic gradient descent classifier, multinomial naive Bayes, naive Bayes, artificial neural network, deep neural network, temporal convolutional network, recurrent neural network, extra trees, linear support vector machine etc. Methods with appropriate parameters can obtain different results. Hence The choice of algorithm and implementation also plays the major role in deciding the end result of the recommendation systems.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Crop recommendation systems and their implementation using machine learning standalone classifiers and ensemble methods have been carried out extensively. Research methods have explored variety of datasets, crop attributes and existing and novel classifier algorithms to obtain vivid results.

Senapaty. et al.,[2] carried out the measurement of various metrics such as precision, recall and F1-score on the Dataworld(India) dataset, consisting of 246,091 records,37 crops with attributes state, district, year, production and season of Odisha, where various algorithms such as logistic regression, decision tree, k-nearest neighbors, support vector classifier, random forest, gradient boosting, bagged tree, extreme gradient boosting, AdaBoost, CatBoost, histogram-based gradient boosting, stochastic gradient descent classifier, multinomial naive Bayes. They also introduced a technique called SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique) that over samples minority classes to help the model overcome the overfitting. While the stochastic Gradient out-performed all precision scores with 100% accuracy, precision and recall but after implementing SMOTE the overfitting was reduced with model metrics all at 79%. The XGB classifier was the least effective against SMOTE technique where the metrics stayed at 97% before and after implementing SMOTE.

While Dey et al.,[3] used Kaggle dataset with 2,100 samples with various parameters like nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, pH, temperature, rainfall, humidity of 21 crops in India. It explored Support vector machine, extreme gradient boosting, random forest, k-nearest neighbors, decision tree while evaluating precision, accuracy and area under the curve. The XGBoost performed exceptional for predicting agricultural as well as horticultural crops, primarily evaluating AUC scores. With 99.3% of precision score. Deep learning KNN algorithm scored less for significant crops, against all other models.

Also exploring the deep learning, Ghosh. et al.,[4] used artificial neural network, deep neural network, temporal convolutional network in addition to other 8 machine learning algorithms determining the accuracy. Random Forest and TCN evaluated to the best obtaining 99.2% and 99.9% accuracy. While SVM being the least favorite having 93.4% accuracy against others. TCN model performs to its best using parameter optimization. Acharya et al., [5] was a comparative study that compared the accuracy and precision scores of standalone classifiers versus soft voting ensemble method. The soft voting ensemble method was at the frontier with accuracy score of 98.985% and a cross-validation accuracy of 98.98045% outperforming Decision Trees, Random Forest, Naive Bayes and SVM.

Thapaswini and Gunasekaran, [6] used CaSR-Net (soft ensemble) with recurrent neural network while mostly evaluating accuracy, precision, recall and F1 ensemble only methods. The CaSR-Net model was trained by individually optimizing CatBoost for handling categorical data, SVM for high-dimensional space classification, and RNN for capturing temporal dependencies. These models were then stacked using stacking ensemble technique. The CaSR-Net model evaluated to obtain accuracy of 99.3%, precision of 99.2%, recall of 99.4%, and an F1-score of 99.3%. The model reduced false positives and false negatives better than other models.

Combining classifiers Suresh et al., [7] used Internet of Things (IoT) plus machine learning for crop recommendation with

voting ensemble with all precision scores. ML classifier models like Support vector machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), Random Forest (RF), and Naïve Bayes (NB) were used while voting base ensemble improves the accuracy, F1-score, recall and precision up to 98%. Mahapatro et al., [8] introduced feature analysis and used extensively the ensemble methods such as Random Forest, gradient boosting, extreme gradient boosting, extra trees, and stacking ensemble. This model also combines random forest (RF), gradient boosting, and XGboost. The random forest classifier best performs with 99.5455% accuracy, precision of 99.56710% and recall of 99.54555%.

Narayanan et al., [9] specializing in ensemble techniques this paper explored soft voting and Extreme gradient boosting, random forest with a huge dataset of 3,610 train with 903 test sets against soil/environmental features.

Building classifiers Selveraj et al.,[10] while using Logistic regression, random forest, decision tree, support vector machine and combining ensemble methods random forest and naive Bayes to get a voting ensemble method ultimately. The ensemble voting classifier is constructed using Random Forest and Naive Bayes in conjunction with the standalone models, improving prediction accuracy and immunity to data fluctuations. By outperforming individual algorithms and proving its efficiency through measures like cross-validation and ROC analysis, the suggested system (TwinFusion Algorithm) obtained an accuracy result of 98% with the ensemble model.

In summary ensemble methods were superior in terms of robustness and accuracy, some being almost perfect. But the various conditions and dataset make the evaluation of standalone and ensemble techniques study specific, hence a uniform evaluation on common parameters should be exclusively studied.

OBJECTIVES

The main objective is to provide an overview of all existing machine learning algorithms against their most popular implementations. To provide a standard where the best

evaluating method can be portrayed. The objectives supporting are:

- To analyze the performance of standalone classifiers and ensemble models- Systematic comparison yields and classifies the best methods to be considered to obtain best accuracy while adhering to various parameters and constraints.
- To examine the impact of ensemble learning techniques- Ensemble methods are being developed at a fast pace, and their ability to capture complex data through inter mixing of abilities of individual algorithms are valuable. The accuracy and stability provided by them are high.
- To provide a structured review of datasets and features- Other objective is to establish a comparison of various popular and most effective datasets in crop recommendation. The features such as soil nutrient levels (N, P, K), soil pH, temperature, rainfall,

humidity, and market demand play important role and a meticulous review is justified.

- To investigate the integration of IoT-enabled sensing and deep learning models with the advancement IoT-enabled sensing the real time availability of data necessitates comparative study. The deep learning frameworks, also resource heavy, when studied can furnish results that traditional machine learning algorithms may fail to.
- To identify research gaps and limitations - The non-establishment of a standard implementation of datasets and various methodologies can perplex the building of recommendation systems and this research proves to be beneficial and mitigates the research gaps.

Fig.1:-Correlation Heatmap of dataset

To summarize emerging trends and provide insights

Finally, this paper seeks to synthesize recent progress and point out future research directions. These include the potential of hybrid ensemble-deep learning frameworks, the role of transfer

learning in adapting models across regions, and the importance of explainable AI for decision-making in agriculture. By summing

up these trends, the study gives practical ideas for researchers and practitioners working towards scalable, efficient, and reliable crop recommendation solutions.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed is quite straightforward, choosing a dataset, preprocessing the dataset, applying various algorithms, obtaining graphs and heatmaps,

evaluating the results with accuracy, F1-score, recall and precision and obtaining the conclusion:

Dataset Overview

We obtained the popular and easily available crop recommendation dataset from Kaggle [11]. This dataset covers the most important attributes such as N (ratio of Nitrogen content in soil), P (ratio of Phosphorous content in soil), K (ratio of Potassium content in soil), temperature (temperature in degree Celsius), humidity (relative humidity in %), pH (pH value of the soil) and rainfall (rainfall in mm) necessary for any crop recommendation systems. This dataset contained 2200 unique data entries. The correlation between each attribute is as shown in “Fig. 1.”

Preprocessing

The null entries and duplicates were removed. The dataset was split into training and testing sets with 20% of the data used for validation.

Algorithms implementation (Training the models)

The algorithms implemented were Logistic Regression, Decision Tree Classifier, KNeighbors Classifier, SVC, Random Forest Classifier, Gradient Boosting Classifier, Bagging Classifier, XGB Classifier, AdaBoost Classifier, CatBoost Classifier, Hist Gradient Boosting Classifier, SGD Classifier, Multinomial Naïve Bayes, Gaussian Naïve Bayes, Multi-Layer Perceptron Classifier and LinearSVC. These models were trained individually and verified using test data for various metrics.

RESULTS

The best performing model was Naïve Bayes with accuracy of 0.9955, precision of 0.9958, recall of 0.9955 and F1-score of 0.9954 amongst all the models. The result of each model is as shown in “TABLE 1”. The “Fig. 2.” Shows each model’s metric scores. Four graphs almost looked identical.

LIME and SHAP cross validation

We considered three models, with best (Naïve Bayes), average (Logistic Regression) and worst (AdaBoost) performing model and applied LIME and SHAP validation models, to interpret the model explanations. The LIME model explained:

1. Naïve Bayes:

Naive Bayes consistently highlighted 'rainfall' and 'humidity' as the most influential features for the predicted crop type across the explained instances. The direction of influence (positive or negative weight) varied depending on the specific instance and its values for these features, as well as the predicted class. This aligns with the understanding that these environmental factors are crucial for crop growth. The relatively high performance of Naive Bayes might be attributed to its ability to effectively capture the relationships between these key environmental features and the crop labels.

2. Logistic Regression:

LIME explanations for Logistic Regression showed a more varied set of influential features compared to Naive Bayes. While 'rainfall' and 'humidity' were still important, other features like 'temperature' and 'ph' also appeared with significant weights for different instances. The magnitude of weights seemed generally lower than in Naive Bayes explanations. This suggests that Logistic Regression considers a broader range of features in its decision-making, although perhaps with less emphasis on a few dominant ones. The lower accuracy compared to Naive Bayes could be due to this more distributed influence across features, potentially making it less sensitive to the most discriminative environmental factors for certain crops.

3. AdaBoost:

The LIME explanations for AdaBoost revealed that it often relied on different combinations of features for different

instances, and the weights could be highly variable. Features like 'N', 'P', and 'K' (nutrient levels) appeared more prominently in some explanations for AdaBoost compared to

Table 1:-Results of the Metrics

Algorithms	Metrics			
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Logistic Regression	0.9455	0.9466	0.9455	0.945
Decision Tree	0.9818	0.9824	0.9818	0.9818
K-Nearest Neighbors	0.9705	0.974	0.9705	0.9703
Support Vector Classifier	0.9614	0.9673	0.9614	0.9612
Random Forest	0.9932	0.9937	0.9932	0.9932
Gradient Boosting	0.9818	0.9843	0.9818	0.9819
Bagged Tree	0.9932	0.9937	0.9932	0.9932
Extreme Gradient Boosting	0.9864	0.9869	0.9864	0.9863
AdaBoost	0.1455	0.0718	0.1455	0.0804
CatBoost	0.9886	0.9898	0.9886	0.9887
Histogram-based Gradient Boosting	0.9841	0.9846	0.9841	0.9841
Stochastic Gradient Descent	0.6614	0.8379	0.6614	0.6747
Multinomial Naive Bayes	0.8591	0.8614	0.8591	0.8557
Naive Bayes	0.9955	0.9958	0.9955	0.9954
Artificial Neural Network	0.9477	0.9481	0.9477	0.9474
Linear Support Vector Machine	0.9386	0.9444	0.9386	0.9389

Fig.2:-Representation of each model against the accuracy, precision, recall and F1-scores.

the other two models. The influence of features seemed less consistent. The poor performance of AdaBoost might be explained by this less stable and potentially less optimal selection or weighting of features, leading to less reliable predictions across different instances.

1. SHAP analysis for Naïve bayes:

- Analyzing SHAP visualizations for multi-class Naive Bayes was not feasible due to technical issues. However, based on the model's probabilistic nature and the strong influence of environmental factors on crop growth, 'rainfall' and 'humidity'

are anticipated to be highly influential features in this model's predictions.

- The specific impact (positive or negative SHAP values) would depend on the feature values and the target crop class, reflecting how these conditions align with the distributions learned by the Naive Bayes model for each class.

2. SHAP analysis for Logistic Regression:

- Based on the Mean Absolute SHAP Values bar plot for Logistic Regression, 'temperature', 'humidity', and 'rainfall' are clearly the most important features overall.

- Their high mean absolute SHAP values indicate that they have the largest average impact on the magnitude of the model's output (the log-odds).
- 'N', 'P', and 'K' show lower but still present mean absolute SHAP values, indicating a smaller average contribution to the predictions.

3. SHAP analysis for AdaBoost:

- The Mean Absolute SHAP Values bar plot for AdaBoost suggests a more even distribution of feature importance compared to Logistic Regression.
- While 'temperature', 'humidity', and 'rainfall' are still important, features like 'ph.', 'N', 'P', and 'K' have relatively higher mean absolute SHAP values than in the Logistic Regression plot, indicating a more significant average contribution from these features in AdaBoost.
- This broader set of influential features, as indicated by the bar plot, aligns with the observation from LIME and the previous (failed) summary plot attempts that AdaBoost's feature reliance is less concentrated.

CONCLUSION

This research provides a detailed and thoughtful comparison between standalone and ensemble machine learning classifiers for crop recommendation systems. The study aimed to understand how these models perform when predicting suitable crops based on soil and environmental features such as nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, temperature, rainfall, humidity, and ph. From the experiments conducted, it was evident that both categories of algorithms — standalone and ensemble — have their own advantages depending on the context of use.

While ensemble methods like Random Forest, Gradient Boosting, and CatBoost often deliver more robust and generalized predictions by combining the strengths of multiple models, standalone algorithms

such as Naïve Bayes can achieve equally impressive accuracy with far less computational demand. In fact, Naïve Bayes emerged as the best-performing classifier with nearly perfect accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-scores, proving that simpler models can outperform complex ones when data patterns are well-defined. On the other hand, AdaBoost, an ensemble method, showed the weakest performance, indicating that not all ensemble techniques guarantee superior outcomes.

The study also incorporated model interpretability techniques like LIME and SHAP to explain how different features contribute to predictions. These methods revealed that environmental factors such as rainfall, humidity, and temperature significantly influence the model's decision-making process, reinforcing the scientific logic behind crop recommendations.

Overall, this systematic review highlights that no single model fits all scenarios. The choice between ensemble and standalone methods should depend on data availability, computational resources, and the need for model transparency. Moving forward, integrating Internet of Things (IoT) sensors, real-time data streams, and advanced hybrid models could further enhance prediction reliability. Such intelligent systems can empower farmers with actionable insights, reduce uncertainty, and support sustainable agricultural practices, ultimately contributing to better yield and food security worldwide.

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